

Overview

The Open Access eBooks Usage Data Trust ([OAeBUDT](#)) seeks clarity around terminology used for usage and impact assessment.

This research plan describes the phases of work for the *EAGER: Secure Research Impact Metric Data Exchange: Data Supply Chain and Vocabulary Development* project ([NSF 2335827](#)), to develop 1) a glossary and 2) a crosswalk to existing vocabularies for key terms related to usage information exchange and use for publicly accessible scholarship outputs.

This is a high-level summary of the timeline, approach and milestones spanning November 2023 through June 2024.

Desk research: November 2023-ongoing

Research and compile (ongoing as needed/as discovered):

- Existing vocabularies, formal and informal
- Individuals, organizations and initiatives involved in usage, for potential engagement
- Literature on the role of usage in impact metrics/assessment

Exploratory interviews: January-March 2024

Initial, semi-structured discussions with key stakeholder representatives

In this phase, individual meetings with representatives of key stakeholder groups are meant to provide input for additional interviews and research.

Each interviewee is introduced to the project (and the OAeBU DT if necessary) and an [April 2023 NSF Workshop](#) where the idea for this work was first raised, as the context for the project. Discussions center on the perspectives, challenges and suggestions of each participant.

Questions common to each of these interviews:

1. Do you use a glossary internally/externally?
 - a. If so, what source(s) do you use?
2. Do these three general categories of usage/metric resonate 1) usage 2) web analytics and 3) assessment/metrics? Or do you consider others?
3. What sources do you rely on or follow for news and information about usage?
4. Would a crosswalk be useful?
 - a. What other kinds of community resources along these lines might?
5. Who else should I talk with about this project?

Synthesizing information gathered: April-May 2024

In this phase, the desk research and interviews to date are analyzed to:

- Review/recalibrate scope as needed
- Check in with consultants Clarke and Esposito, who are working on a companion project
- Review project to date with OAeBUDT stakeholders:
 - Board of Trustees
 - Technical Advisory Committee
- **Draft initial documents for review** with meeting participants:
 - Glossary of key terms, citing source vocabularies
 - Vocabularies crosswalk resource of key term definitions across existing vocabularies
- **Convene a meeting/focus group of interested stakeholders** based on research and interviews to discuss:
 - Definitions
 - Synonyms
 - Gaps
 - Any missing stakeholders or vocabularies
 - Role(s) in impact assessment
 - What resources on these topics are most useful to them

Community review and revision: May-June 2024

In this phase, input from the wider community is sought on outputs before they are revised, finalized and distributed. It includes:

- **Communicating about the project broadly**
- **Sharing resulting outputs for community comment**
 - Refining based on feedback
 - Ideally, taking opportunities at conferences to share project information for feedback

Sharing results: Summer 2024

- Sharing final outputs in Zenodo
- Communicating the results